

Measles Vaccine Acceptance and Disease Persistence in Cameroon: Findings from a Nationwide Cross-Sectional Survey

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Keywords: Measles, elimination, vaccine acceptance, Cameroon

IGOs: United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), World
Health Organization (WHO)

Submitted: 01/17/2026

Approved: 02/16/2026

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19064452>

Citation: Njoh, A. A., Hagos, Z., Bamidele, M. A., Kongnyuy, E. J.,
Cantave, F., Madaina, I., Ndoula, S. T., & Cleenewerck de Kiev, L.
(2026). Measles vaccine acceptance and disease persistence in
Cameroon: Findings from a nationwide cross-sectional survey.
The Intergovernmental Research and Policy Journal, 13(1).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19064452>

ABSTRACT

Measles remains a highly contagious disease and a leading cause of death among young children, despite the availability of effective vaccines. In Cameroon, suboptimal immunization coverage has contributed to persistent outbreaks. This study assessed the role of vaccine acceptance in the country's low vaccination coverage.

A nationwide cross-sectional survey was conducted from January to November 2025 using online and in-person questionnaires. Data from 2,169 participants were analyzed using chi-square tests and multiple logistic regression, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Overall measles vaccine acceptance was high (99%), with regional variations highest in the Far North and lowest in the South West and West Regions. Hesitancy was associated with concerns about vaccine safety, misinformation on social media, and limited knowledge. Key determinants of acceptance included participants' understanding of measles (OR = 28, 95% CI: 11–76, $p < 0.01$) and history of measles-related deaths (OR = 0.4, 95% CI: 0.2–0.8, $p < 0.01$), while family history of infection showed no significant association.

Despite high acceptance rates, measles remains a major public health concern in Cameroon. Strengthening immunization service delivery and leveraging existing public willingness to vaccinate are critical to improving coverage and advancing measles elimination.

1. Introduction

Measles is a highly infectious viral disease that affects unimmunized people, and it is most common in children, leading to severe disease, complications, and death.¹ Ongoing efforts have led to a remarkable reduction in measles cases since 1990.² Despite this progress, millions of people are infected with measles yearly. Although there are safe and cost-effective vaccines, about 95,000 people died from measles in 2024, most of whom were children under five years old.³

There is an alarming rise in measles cases, with a significant burden in resource-constrained settings, reflecting declining vaccination coverage.⁴ The African Region has been severely affected by measles in recent years.⁵ About half of major outbreaks occur in the World Health Organization's African region, with a considerable number of registered child deaths.⁶ Sub-Saharan African nations have been suffering from outbreaks with a massive number of measles cases recorded following the 2019 coronavirus disease (COVID-19), and

countries continue to put in great efforts to control the disease.⁷ The disease affects every nation, with a significant burden in countries, like Cameroon.

Cameroon has been affected by measles, with a significant burden on the population and health systems over the years.⁸ The country has been experiencing a remarkable resurgence of measles cases in recent years, causing dozens of deaths.⁹ The recurrent measles outbreaks are exacerbated by disrupted immunization services. The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic limited vaccination services, leaving many unvaccinated and undervaccinated, and hindering disease control in this nation, favoring measles outbreaks.¹⁰ The country has pockets of unvaccinated children in various parts, susceptible to disease.¹¹ Armed violence in parts of the country left many unvaccinated, which favored disease spread and deaths.¹²

In this situation, the country is undertaking efforts to control the disease, including strengthening disease surveillance and expanding vaccination coverage.¹³ Cameroon health workers

¹ WHO, 'Measles', 28 November 2025, 1, <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/measles>.

² Ruitong Wang et al., 'Trends of the Global, Regional, and National Incidence of Measles, Vaccine Coverage, and Risk Factors in 204 Countries From 1990 to 2019', *Frontiers in Medicine* 8 (January 2022): 3, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2021.798031>.

³ WHO, 'Measles', 1.

⁴ eClinicalMedicine, 'Concerning Global Rise in Measles Cases', *eClinicalMedicine* 68 (February 2024): 1, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eclinm.2024.102502>.

⁵ Goodluck Nchasi et al., 'Measles Outbreak in Sub-Saharan Africa amidst COVID-19: A Rising Concern, Efforts, Challenges, and Future Recommendations', *Annals of Medicine and Surgery* 81 (September 2022): 1, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amsu.2022.104264>.

⁶ Evans Mpabalwani et al., 'Global Resurgence of Measles: Turning the Tide through a Bold Agenda for Prevention and Control', *International Journal of Infectious Diseases: IJID: Official Publication of the International Society for Infectious Diseases* 155 (June 2025): 1, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2025.107901>.

⁷ Nchasi et al., 'Measles Outbreak in Sub-Saharan Africa amidst COVID-19', 1–2.

⁸ Haddison C. Eposi et al., 'Measles Outbreak Investigation in a Highly Vaccinated Community in the Centre Region of Cameroon', *Journal of Public Health in Africa* 12, no. 1 (2021): 1–2, <https://doi.org/10.4081/jphia.2021.1775>.

⁹ Florence Irita et al., 'Recrudescence of Measles Cases in Children under 5 Years of Age and Associated Factors in the Health District of Logbaba, Cameroon: An Unpaired Case-Control Study', *Discover Public Health* 22, no. 1 (2025): 3, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12982-025-00778-1>.

¹⁰ Etienne Gignoux et al., 'Measles: The Long Walk to Elimination Drawn out by COVID-19', *The Lancet Global Health* 9, no. 3 (2021): 1, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(21\)00020-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(21)00020-6).

¹¹ Tsi Njim et al., 'Measles Outbreak in a Poorly Vaccinated Region in Cameroon: A Case Series Study, Public Health Challenges and Recommendations', *The Pan African Medical Journal* 22, no. 163 (2015): 2, <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2015.22.163.8015>.

¹² Esum Mathias Eyong et al., 'Factors Associated with Measles Outbreak in Three Health Districts of Cameroon in 2019: A Cross-Sectional Study', *The Pan African Medical Journal* 46, no. 41 (2023): 2–3, 41, <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2023.46.41.35832>.

¹³ Andreas Ateke Njoh et al., 'Impact of Periodic Intensification of Routine Immunization within an Armed Conflict Setting and COVID-19 Outbreak in Cameroon in 2020', *Conflict and Health* 16, no. 1 (2022): 2–4, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13031-022-00461-1>.

have been capacitated, and the health system strengthened for the detection and diagnosis of priority diseases, including measles.¹⁴ In addition, the nation has made significant strides in improving first-dose measles vaccination coverage and introducing the second dose for children aged 15 months and older since 2020.

Cameroon has been experiencing a long-term upward trend in vaccination coverage. However, coverages remain sub-optimal.¹⁵ Due to persisting immunity gaps, the country experiences outbreaks yearly, particularly in regions with lower vaccination coverage, resulting in substantial cases and fatalities.¹⁶ Despite the availability of an effective measles and rubella vaccine in Cameroon, the reasons for low coverage rates remain unclear. This study, therefore, aimed to investigate measles vaccine acceptance and the key factors contributing to vaccine hesitancy in the country.

2. Methodology

2.1 Study design

This cross-sectional nationwide survey was conducted in Cameroon. The study collected data from participants across the country's ten regions from January to November 2025. KoboToolbox online questionnaire permitted data collection.

2.2 Study setting

In 2025, the country had nearly 30 million inhabitants across its ten regions.¹⁷ According to the national population

estimates, the most populous regions include the Far North, the Center, and the Littoral. The regions are divided into divisions, which are further subdivided into health districts, each of which is coordinated by a district medical officer. Health districts and health areas (subdistrict units) have dialogue structures led by a community leader. At least three of the country's regions have been experiencing some degree of armed violence for nearly ten years, affecting immunization services. The affected areas include the South West and North West in sociopolitical crisis, and the Far North, experiencing periodic attacks from Boko Haram.¹⁸

2.3 Study questionnaire

An online questionnaire in KoboToolbox enabled data collection across Cameroon's 10 regions. Following pretesting of the questionnaire on 30 participants recruited from the country's ten regions, the questions were revised to improve clarity and ensure internal consistency. The questionnaire had a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.74, indicating stronger agreement among items.

The questionnaire was available in English and French, the two most widely spoken languages in the country. In addition, questions were semi-open-ended, allowing respondents to select their answers and add more responses to the questions as needed. The proposed answers were inspired by a previous study on malaria vaccine acceptance that identified common

¹⁴ CDC, 'CDC in Cameroon | Global Health', 9 December 2025, 1–2, <https://www.cdc.gov/global-health/countries/cameroon.html>.

¹⁵ Mathurin Cyrille Tejiokem et al., 'Pre- and Post-Vaccination Measles Antibody and Persistence Up to 5 Years of Age Among Early ART-Treated HIV-Infected, HIV-Exposed Uninfected and HIV-Unexposed Children in Cameroon', *Vaccines* 13, no. 6 (2025): 1, <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines13060584>.

¹⁶ Samantha Nyakundi, 'Zero-Dose Children and Vaccine Gaps in Cameroon', *Think Global Health*, 25 November 2025, 1–2,

<https://www.thinkglobalhealth.org/article/zero-dose-children-and-vaccine-gaps-in-cameroon>.

¹⁷ World Population Review, 'Cameroon Population 2025', 1, accessed 6 January 2026, <https://worldpopulationreview.com/countries/cameroon>.

¹⁸ OCHA, 'Cameroon Humanitarian Update - September 2025 | OCHA', 7 November 2025, 1, <https://www.unocha.org/publications/report/cameroon/cameroon-humanitarian-update-september-2025>.

factors underlying vaccine acceptance and hesitancy in Cameroon.¹⁹

The responses were anonymous. The questionnaire collected participants' information, including region of residence, type of residential community (rural/urban), gender, occupation, and income level. The design used Gapminder's four-level income classification for income grading.²⁰ The tool KoboToolbox also collected data on participants' measles vaccine knowledge, family history of measles, and death. In addition, the form assessed participants' willingness to vaccinate their children against measles and the reasons for their acceptance or refusal of the vaccine. All questions were compulsory to complete. Participants could not submit the form online if all questions were not answered.

2.4 Study sample Size

The Raosoft sample size calculator eased the estimation of the minimum sample size.²¹ The estimate considered a 5% error margin, a 95% confidence interval, and a Cameroon population of nearly 30 million to determine the minimum sample size needed to obtain adequate, statistically significant data. These parameters gave a minimum sample size of 385 participants. More people were, however, surveyed to ensure proper statistical analysis across the variables. Additionally, the design ensured that participants were represented from all 58 divisions across the country's 10 regions, thereby highlighting national representation in the data analysis.

2.5 Participants recruitment

Participants were recruited through the Cameroon Ministry of Health's existing dialogue structure. The study was presented

to national-level, regional, and district health managers. These actors informed the population in their health communities through dialogue structures about the survey, its benefits, the time constraints for participants, and the need for personal internet to submit the responses. A simple random sampling permitted the recruitment of participants in the various dialogue structure levels. The questionnaire was shared with interested parties via social media platforms such as WhatsApp. Respondents considered in the study were those aged 21 and older who consented to participate.

2.6 Data analysis

SPSS was used for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics permitted highlighting the distribution of demographic and other characteristics among respondents. The Chi-square test was used to identify the association between the variables and the acceptance of the measles vaccine. All analyses were binary, based on whether respondents were willing to have their children vaccinated against measles. Additional comments and explanations from participants for each question were grouped by similarity and reported in proportions using Excel.

The vaccine acceptance rate was the proportion of respondents willing to vaccinate their children against measles for each indicator and locality, expressed in absolute numbers and as a proportion of respondents for that indicator. Additionally, the reasons for accepting or denying the vaccine were graded based on respondents' comments using a semi-open-ended question, "Why will you accept to vaccinate your child against measles?" and "Why will you not accept to vaccinate your child against measles?" for those who were hesitant to vaccinate their children. Multiple logistic

¹⁹ Andreas Ateke Njoh et al., 'Malaria Vaccine Acceptance and Associated Factors in Cameroon: A Nationwide Cross-Sectional Survey', *Vaccine* 60 (July 2025): 2, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2025.127323>.

²⁰ Gapminder, *Four Regions*, n.d., 5, accessed 12 July 2023, <https://www.gapminder.org/fw/four-regions/>.

²¹ Raosoft, 'Sample Size Calculator by Raosoft, Inc.', Raosoft, Inc, 2004, 1, <http://www.raosoft.com/samplesize.html>.

regression helped in identifying factors associated with vaccine acceptance. All statistical tests were performed at a p-value < 0.05. Microsoft Excel 365 was used to elaborate on charts and tables.

This research obtained ethical clearance from the Cameroon National Ethics Committee for Research on Human Health, No 2024/07/1699/CE/CNERSH/SP.

3. Results

Responses from 2169 participants in Cameroon's ten regions were captured in KoboToolbox. The measles vaccine acceptance rate varied per region. The highest acceptance rate was observed in the Far North, while the lowest rates were recorded in the South West and West Regions (97%) (Table 1).

Table 1: Population characteristics and vaccine acceptance (Chi-square): N=2169

Indicator	Responses	n	Vaccine acceptance (%)	p-value
Locality	Adamawa	127	126(99)	0.1
	Center	390	138(99)	
	East	168	165(98)	
	Far North	332	331(100)	
	Littoral	126	124(98)	
	North	151	148(98)	
	North West	305	303(99)	
	West	121	117(97)	
	South	302	300(99)	
	South West	147	143(97)	
Cameroon	2169	2144(99)		
Residence type	Rural	1299	1287(99)	0.2
	Urban	870	857(99)	
Gender	Female	966	955(99)	0.9
	Male	1203	1189(99)	
Age group (years)	18-27	203	196(97)	0.02*
	28-37	698	691(99)	
	38-47	694	687(99)	
	48-57	470	467(99)	
	58 and above	104	103(99)	

Monthly income level	Low (<\$56)	897	882(98)	0.1
	Medium (\$56-200)	718	710(99)	
	High (\$201-830)	520	518(100)	
	Higher (>\$830)	34	33(100)	
Measles knowledge	No	62	51(82)	<0.01*
	Yes	2077	2064(99)	
Use of traditional remedies	No	1979	1959(99)	0.04*
	Yes	190	185(97)	
History of measles in family	No	1193	1181(99)	<0.01*
	Yes	686	679(99)	
History of measles death	I don't know	246	241(98)	<0.01*
	No	1870	1842(99)	
	Yes	159	156(98)	
	I don't know	140	128(91)	

*Statistically significant value, \$: US Dollars

Table 1 presents indicators associated with parents' acceptance of the measles vaccine for their children, as determined by the chi-square test.

Nearly 99% of the participants in Cameroon were willing to vaccinate their children against measles. A greater proportion of those who knew about measles were willing to vaccinate their children against the disease (Table 1). Although the vaccine acceptance rate was high in people using traditional remedies to address measles, people not using traditional remedies to control measles were more willing to vaccinate their children.

Figure 1 illustrates the primary reasons and additional elements cited by participants for accepting to vaccinate their children against measles.

Figure 1: Reason for vaccine acceptance for infants

Various factors motivated participants' willingness to have their children vaccinated against measles. Key motives included protecting their children and loved ones, preventing the spread of measles, and controlling disease.

Figure 2 presents the reasons why participants were hesitant to have their children vaccinated against measles.

Figure 2: Reason for measles vaccine hesitancy

The principal reasons for vaccine hesitancy included concerns about vaccine safety, confusing social media messaging, and insufficient information about the vaccine. Other reasons included distrust of vaccine manufacturers, difficulty accessing vaccination facilities, and distrust of the health system, health workers, and the government. Religious beliefs also posed a challenge to accepting the vaccine.

Table 2: Determinants of measles vaccine acceptance for children using multivariate logistic regression

Variable	p-value	OR	95% CI
Age group(<28)	<0.01*	1.7	0.5-6.1
Age group(28-37)	0.01*	1.4	0.4-5.5
Age group(38-47)	0.69	2.1	0.5-9.9
Age group(48-57)	0.79	0.9	0.1-9.6
Measles knowledge	<0.01*	28.3	10.5-76.3
Use of traditional remedies	0.03*	0.4	0.1-1.4
Family history of measles death	<0.01*	0.4	0.2-0.8
Measles family history	0.29	1.3	0.6-2.5
Occupation	<0.01*	0.9	0.8-1.2

*Statistically significant

Table 2 highlights the key determinants that influence parents' acceptance of measles vaccination for their children.

Considering age as a covariate, participants' knowledge of measles (OR = 28, 95% CI: 11-76, $P < 0.01$), family history of measles death, and the use of traditional remedies to address measles were key factors influencing their willingness to accept the vaccine for their children (Table 2). People of the lower age groups had the highest odds of accepting the vaccine for their children.

There was no statistically significant association between family history of measles infection and family history of measles infection and vaccine acceptance.

4. Discussion

Measles is a highly infectious viral disease with a significant burden in resource-constrained settings, such as Cameroon. Although the country has made considerable progress in reducing the disease burden over the years following the introduction of two doses of measles-rubella vaccine and the strengthening of disease surveillance and response, the disease persists in a context of suboptimal immunization coverage.²² This study aimed to evaluate the impact of measles vaccine acceptance and the key factors contributing to vaccine hesitancy in the country.

Vaccine acceptance data from 2169 participants showed a nationwide measles vaccination rate of 99%. The highest acceptance rates were observed in the Far North and the lowest in the South West and West Regions (Table 1). Various elements motivated vaccine acceptance, including the desire to protect their children and loved ones, prevent the spread of measles, and mitigate disease risk (Figure 1). However, some people were hesitant to vaccinate their children due to concerns about vaccine safety, confusing social media messaging, and insufficient information about the vaccine (Figure 2). Measles knowledge and a history of measles death and measles-related deaths were associated with parents' acceptance of vaccinating their children, as determined by the chi-square analysis. However, residence region, residential

neighborhood (rural/urban), gender, and income level did not have a statistically significant impact on vaccine acceptance (Table 1). Participants' understanding of measles (OR = 2.8, 95% CI: 1.1-7.6, $P < 0.01$) and a history of measles death were key determinants of vaccine acceptance for children (Table 2).

Vaccine acceptance is crucial to vaccine uptake and vaccination coverage. Parents' willingness to accept the measles vaccine drives vaccine uptake and ultimately helps prevent disease. This study identified a very high vaccine acceptance rate, with the least regions recording 97% acceptance (South West and West). Unfortunately, the country's vaccination coverage has been at <80% for the first dose and <50% for the second measles-containing vaccine doses for years now, as reported by the WHO 2024 immunization dashboard.²³ These rates are far from the 95% measles vaccination coverage needed to stop transmission and protect communities from measles outbreaks.²⁴ This high acceptance and low coverage is not surprising, given that the country faces challenges, including vaccine stockouts, long distances to health facilities, and a limited health worker workforce to sustain routine immunization.²⁵

Despite this high vaccine acceptance, hesitancy persists. Vaccine hesitancy is a major threat to global health and also contributes to a rise in unvaccinated people and measles outbreaks.²⁶ The main reasons for vaccine hesitancy were concerns about vaccine safety, confusing social media messaging, insufficient information about the vaccine, distrust in health systems and vaccine manufacturers, and challenges

²² Tejiokem et al., 'Pre- and Post-Vaccination Measles Antibody and Persistence Up to 5 Years of Age Among Early ART-Treated HIV-Infected, HIV-Exposed Uninfected and HIV-Unexposed Children in Cameroon', 1.

²³ WHO, 'WHO Immunization Data Portal - African Region', Immunization Data, 1, accessed 7 January 2026, <https://immunizationdata.who.int/dashboard/regions/african-region>.

²⁴ WHO, 'Measles Deaths down 88% since 2000, but Cases Surge', 28 November 2025, 1, <https://www.who.int/news/item/28-11-2025-measles-deaths-down-88--since-2000--but-cases-surge>.

²⁵ Nyakundi, 'Zero-Dose Children and Vaccine Gaps in Cameroon', 2.

²⁶ WHO, 'Ten Threats to Global Health in 2019', 3, accessed 7 January 2026, <https://www.who.int/news-room/spotlight/ten-threats-to-global-health-in-2019>.

accessing health facilities. Social media amplifies vaccine misinformation, allowing anti-vaccine activists to sow doubt about the safety of the measles vaccine despite available scientific consensus of its safety and efficacy.²⁷ Monitoring social media messages and addressing the concerns of specific population groups is critical to improving measles vaccination rates. Improving population sensitization and using corrective messages will help debunk misinformation.²⁸

Distrust in the healthcare system and vaccine manufacturing negatively impacts vaccination rates. Addressing this issue requires a multifaceted approach that acknowledges the underlying worries contributing to these sentiments.²⁹ Strategies that focus on building and maintaining trust through appropriate communication, transparency, and community engagement are crucial.

In addition, making vaccines accessible to all is crucial for improving vaccination coverage in this setting, where people often face challenges in accessing some health facilities. Community engagement, logistical planning, effective communication, and integrated services are crucial for reaching individuals with limited access to the healthcare system. Engaging in outreach integrated health packages, including vaccination sessions, will help get children in Cameroon who missed their routine measles vaccination dose.³⁰

Knowledge of measles and its potential disease severity is critical to the acceptance of vaccination. Parents' understanding of vaccine safety and efficacy shapes their willingness to vaccinate their children.³¹ The population needs to be provided with the appropriate message to build their knowledge and foster vaccine acceptance. Additionally, capitalizing on the vaccine acceptance points while addressing hesitancy will sustain vaccine uptake in this nation.

This study assessed nationwide measles vaccine acceptance and hesitancy in Cameroon and provides considerations for strengthening measles vaccination nationwide. In addition, the study is the first to highlight nationwide measles vaccine hesitancy, which many believe is the key contributor to low vaccination coverage. Despite these merits, the study has some limitations. Firstly, it assesses vaccine acceptance; however, the willingness to vaccinate children does not indicate that they will actually be vaccinated. Additionally, the study utilized an online form, which may have excluded some individuals without access to a mobile phone or computer from participating. However, volunteers collected population data in areas with low response rates to mitigate this bias. Despite these weaknesses, this study lays the groundwork for investigating other factors, including supply-site elements, that may be key contributors to low measles vaccination coverage and the failure to eliminate the disease in Cameroon.

²⁷ Adekunle F. Adeoye et al., 'The 2025 United States Measles Crisis: When Vaccine Hesitancy Meets Reality', *Cureus* 17 (July 2025): 2, <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.88196>.

²⁸ Yi-Lun Jheng et al., 'Strategies to Correct Vaccine Misinformation on Social Media for Pregnant Women and the Impact of Vaccine Skepticism', *Scientific Reports* 15, no. 1 (2025): 8, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-98709-2>.

²⁹ Toni Z. Madorsky et al., 'Vaccine Distrust: A Predictable Response to Structural Racism and an Inadequate Public Health Infrastructure', *American Journal of Public Health* 111, no. Suppl 3 (2021): 4, <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2021.306411>.

³⁰ WHO, 'Reaching the Unreached: Outreach Vaccination for Children in Viet Nam's Remote Areas', 18 January 2024, 1, <https://www.who.int/westernpacific/newsroom/feature-stories/item/reaching-the-unreached--outreach-vaccination-for-children-in-viet-nam-s-remote-areas>.

³¹ Jessica Kaufman et al., 'The Case for Assessing the Drivers of Measles Vaccine Uptake', *Vaccines* 12, no. 6 (2024): 1–2, <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines12060692>.

5. Conclusion

Measles is a highly infectious viral disease that poses a significant burden in Cameroon and globally. Seeking to assess the reasons for the failure to eliminate the disease in Cameroon, this study found that communities exhibit low levels of vaccine hesitancy. While capitalizing on the reasons for vaccine acceptance and addressing key vaccine hesitancy points in Cameroon, it is critical to investigate supply-side factors to improve vaccination coverage and address the ongoing measles outbreaks.

6. Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest that could have influenced this research.

7. Acknowledgment

The regional and district managers of the Cameroon Ministry of Health, as well as the community dialogue structure leaders who facilitated this research. The research participants are acknowledged for their time and their collaboration in using their personal internet to access and submit the questionnaire online.

8 Funding

The Njoh Foundation (TNF 202504) funded this research.

8. Availability of data and materials

The database used during this study is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

9. List of abbreviations

COVID-19: 2019 Coronavirus disease, **WHO:** World Health Organization

10. Contributions

AAN conceived the study's idea and design and elaborated on the first draft. AAN and IM contributed to data collection and analysis. AAN, ZH, MAB, EJK, FC, and STN revised subsequent drafts. LCK inspired, supervised the research, and guided the preparation of the article. All authors reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript.

11. Ethics declarations and consent to participate

This study received ethical clearance for the research from the National Ethics Committee for Research on Human Health, No 2024/07/1699/CE/CNERSH/SP. Participants consented after understanding the research goal, being informed that there was no risk, and knowing that participating would require them to dedicate their time and use the internet.

12. Consent for publication

Not applicable.

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